

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

USE OF ANALYTICAL-CALCULUS METHODOLOGY FOR CALCULATION OF FROZEN GROUND THAWING OF OPEN GROUND

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Abstract

The paper proposes an approach of analytical structure of the solution of the mathematical model of heat transfer in two-dimensional formulation, based on the principles of the finite element method. The essence of which is that the analytical solution in each element of the domain is constructed through linearly independent partial solutions of the heat transfer equation, which is expressed through the shape functions and through the nodal points of the element. The size of the elements does not affect the accuracy of the results because the analytical solution in each element is known. The nodal values can be the boundary conditions of the process under study. Whereas in the finite element method (FEM) the accuracy of the results depends on the size of each element because the analytical expression of the approximate solution of the mathematical model is constructed through arbitrary polynomials that are not partial solutions of the heat transfer equation. As a result, the combination of the analytical method with the FEM allowed to get rid of the question of the element size, automatic satisfaction of the initial boundary conditions. Satisfaction of the initial condition allowed to identify the parameters of the mathematical model, in particular, as the coefficients of thermal diffusivity and heat transfer. The validity of the proposed approach was verified by solving the applied problem and comparing the results with in-situ observation data.

Keywords: Thermal conductivity coefficient, heat transfer coefficient, frozen and thawed soils, m.c.e., analytical solutions, analytic-calculus solution, homogeneous and inhomogeneous media.

The development of efficient methods for solving applied problems is one of the key objectives of applied research. This paper considers the problem of determining the thawing zone of frozen ground at the Kumtor mine site, located at an altitude of 3800m, under the influence of ambient temperature during the warm period of the year (from March to September).

The peculiarity of this problem is that the boundary condition on the day surface is given by the ambient temperature obtained from the Kumtor weather station, which is measured daily three times a day.

In analytical methods, the boundary and initial conditions must be approximated in the form of a functional dependence, which depends on the complexity of

their setting. In the proposed analytical solution, due to the presence of the FEM idea, boundary and initial conditions are considered as they are in point form.

Problem Statement. The investigated area is schematically represented in Fig.1. with a width of 120m and a height of 40m. It is divided into five triangular elements. The depth of the first triangular element is 40m. The initial condition for the day surface temperature is set to +2.65 °C. The zero isotherm in Fig. 1 is shown by the red line. Permafrost begins at a depth of 30 meters from the day surface with a temperature of -2°C. It is required to determine the coefficient of thermal diffusivity and the movement of the permafrost thawing front.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of the area

Algorithm of analytical and numerical methodology for solving the problem of frozen ground thawing and determining the thermal conductivity coefficient

As it is known according to [1, 2] the process of melting of frozen ground is mathematically modeled by the heat conduction equation

$$\frac{\partial T_T}{\partial t} = a_T \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_T}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

And the corresponding initial boundary conditions. The melting line is located by the location of the zero isotherm.

The analytical solution in an arbitrary triangular element is constructed through basis functions, which are partial solutions of the heat conduction equation (1). Linearly independent partial solutions of the heat conduction equation (1) are used as basis functions

$$T_1(x, y, t, a) = e^{-\left(\frac{x+y}{\sqrt{a}}\right)} \cos\left(\left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{a}}\right)\left(\frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{ly}\right) + 4\pi^2 t \left(\frac{1}{lx^2} + \frac{1}{ly^2}\right)\right),$$

$$T_2(x, t, a) = e^{-\left(\frac{x+y}{\sqrt{a}}\right)} \sin\left(\left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{a}}\right)\left(\frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{ly}\right) + 4\pi^2 t \left(\frac{1}{lx^2} + \frac{1}{ly^2}\right)\right). \quad (2)$$

The type of the partial solution is chosen so that it corresponds to the physics of the process, i.e., the ground temperature decreases in depth and periodically changes in time. At each element an analytical solution is constructed according to the FEM idea through partial solutions (2)

$$T_{T_{\text{eop}}}(x, y, t) = N_i^l(x, y, t)T_i + N_j^l(x, y, t)T_j + N_k^l(x, y, t)T_k \quad (3)$$

where $N_i^l(x, y, t), N_j^l(x, y, t), N_k^l(x, y, t)$ - are analogs of the shape function in FEM, T_i, T_j, T_k are temperature values at the nodal points,

$$N_i = \frac{T_1(x_j, y_j, t, a, lx, ly, \pi) \cdot T_2(x_k, y_k, t, a, lx, ly, \pi) - T_1(x_k, y_k, t, a, lx, ly, \pi) \cdot T_2(x_j, y_j, t, a, lx, ly, \pi)}{\Delta} + \frac{(T_2(x_j, y_j, t, a, lx, ly, \pi) - T_2(x_k, y_k, t, a, lx, ly, \pi))}{\Delta} \cdot T_1(x, y, t, a, lx, ly, \pi) + \left(\frac{T_1(x_k, y_k, t, a, lx, ly, \pi)}{\Delta} - \frac{T_1(x_j, y_j, t, a, lx, ly, \pi)}{\Delta} \right) \cdot T_2(x, y, t, a, lx, ly, \pi);$$

Here the analogs of the FEM shape function take values at $x_i, y_i, N_i = 1, N_j = 0, N_k = 0$, etc.

Determination of the diffusivity coefficient. Satisfying the initial condition of the temperature observation data T_i^{obs} by the method of least squares we find the diffusivity coefficient "a" from the functional (4).

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^n [T_{T_{\text{eop}}}(x, y, 0, a) - T_i^{\text{obs}}]^2 \Rightarrow \min a \quad (4)$$

After determining the coefficient "a" using the solution (3), the locations of the zero isotherm are found.

The reliability of the proposed algorithm were checked by solving the test problem given in [1] The obtained calculations were compared with the exact data of the test problem. Comparison of the results is shown in Fig. 1 in the form of a graph. As can be seen from Fig. 1, the comparison shows a good agreement between them, which shows the reliability and performance of the proposed methodology.

Figure 2. Graph comparing the results of test and analytic-numerical methodology

Solution methodology. The solution domain is considered as a geometrical model composed of five triangular finite elements, which allows approximating the shape of the investigated soil area taking into account its spatial heterogeneity. The heat transfer process is mathematically modeled by equation (1) and initial conditions. Boundary conditions are set on the day surface by the value of ambient temperature according to Kumtor weather station and on the lower

boundary ($y=0$) the permafrost temperature of -20°C is set. Analytical solution of the problem for each triangular element is written by formula (3).

Research results. Calculations of permafrost ground thawing were carried out for the warm period of the year from May to September. The time step was taken equal to one week. Therefore, the temperature value from the weather station data formed the average weekly temperature (tab.1)

Table 1.

Average weekly temperature for 4 months								
Months	May				June			
t (weeks)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
T°C	+2,65	+1,25	+1,77	+1,04	+1,26	+2,53	+4,09	4,17
Months	July				August			
t (weeks)	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
T°C	+3,61	+3,65	+6,50	+4,81	+6,66	+3,97	+4,58	+6,98

The results of determining the zero isotherm are shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen from Fig. 3 during 4 months the depth of melting reached from 2.52 m. to

1.33 m. from the day surface at a given ambient temperature. According to the drawing, the melting depth is the difference of the relief coordinate and the beginning of the zero isotherm.

Figure 3: Depth of frozen ground thawing depending on the ambient temperature

Conclusion. The obtained results agree with the data obtained in [1, 2, 3, 5], which confirms the reliability of the algorithm of the mathematical model realization by the proposed approach.

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